

ISic1133

I.Sicily inscription 1133

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 143

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Πόπλιος] Κορνήλι[ος] Ποπλίου υἱὸς Σκιπίων]
2. [Ἀφρικανὸς ὕπατος ἐλῶν Καρχηδὸνα κατὰ]
3. [κρά]τος τοὺς ἐξ Ἰμέρ[ας ἀνδριάντας]
4. Ἰμεραίο[ις][---]

Apparatus

Text of IG Termini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492747

EDCS 39102291

PHI 140619

Bibliography

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